

Intuition Synergism: A Literature Survey

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ABSTRACT

In this research paper our topic is about Intuition Synergism. The reason of keeping name as Intuition Synergism is the meaning of intuition is ability to understand something instinctively. And meaning of synergism is the interaction or cooperation of two or more organizations, substances, or other agents to produce a combined effect greater than the sum of their separate effects. Here [2] actually the awesome power of synergism is its creativity.

Intuition is the ability to acquire knowledge without proof, evidence, or conscious reasoning, or without understanding how the knowledge was acquired[2][3]. Different writers give the word "intuition" a great variety of different meanings, ranging from direct access to unconscious knowledge, unconscious cognition, inner sensing, inner insight to unconscious pattern-recognition and the ability to understand something instinctively, without the need for conscious reasoning[4][5]. There are philosophers who contend that the word "intuition" is often misunderstood or misused to mean instinct, truth, belief, meaning but rather realms of greater knowledge and other subjects, whereas others contend that faculties such as instinct, belief and intuition are factually related[6][7].

Keywords: Artificial Intelligent, Sixth Sense Technology, Synergism, Machine learning, Robotics, Automation.

INTRODUCTION

In this topic there is a synergism of two intuitive components.

- 1) Artificial Intelligent.
- 2) Sixth Sense Technology.

Artificial Intelligence

The Artificial Intelligence subjects involves in the Computer Science. It is a science and engineer of making intelligent machine that works and reacts like human being.

Artificial Intelligence is a very broad area. Many researches [2] are taking place in the field of Artificial Intelligence. Some of the activities of computers with artificial intelligence are designed for which include Knowledge, Reasoning, Problem Solving, Planning, Learning, Perception, Ability to Move Objects. The Programming language used to develop A.I is Lisp, Prolog, Planner, IPL, STRIPS, and POP11.

The major problems [2] of A.I are

- Reasoning.
When the system is required to do something that it has not been explicitly told how to do, it must reason - it must figure out what it needs to know from what it already knows. For instance, suppose an information retrieval program 'knows' only that Robins are birds and that all birds have wings. Keep in mind that for a system to know these facts means only that it contains data structures and procedures that would allow it to answer the questions:
- Automation planning and scheduling.
The realization of strategies or action sequences, typically for execution by intelligent agents, autonomous robots and unmanned vehicles
- Machine Learning.
System will learn from you, the user, which will help it grow and evolve over time enhancing its own knowledge and. unique personality

- Natural Language processing.
Interact with our system the same way you interact with other people – through voice and gestures. Interact with our system the same way you interact with other people – through voice.
- Computer vision
It is branch of AI which recognizes your face or any other shape within an instance.
- Robotics.
Robotics is the branch of mechanical engineering, electrical engineering and computer science that deals with the design, construction, operation, and application of robots as well as computer systems for their control, sensory feedback, and information processing.
- Knowledge Representation.
To representing information about the world in a form that a computer system can utilize to solve complex tasks. Knowledge representation incorporates findings from psychology about how humans solve problems and represent knowledge in order to design formalisms that will make complex systems easier to design and build.

The modern approaches are

- Neural Network.
- Bayesian Network.
- Evolutionary Algorithm.

Sixth-Sense Technology

This technology even helps workplace or home of the future where computing is extended to encompass non-computing entities such as people, objects, and spaces to enable rich user experiences. For instance, we would like users to be able to search the physical world for objects they may have misplaced or use physical events to index their experiences.

The history of “6th sense technology” goes back into 1990’s when Steve Mann first attempted to propose a neck worn projector and camera combination. The sixth sense technology is a wearable device that captures the gesture and augments it in the physical world around us with digital information and let us to use hand gesture to interact to that gesture. The Programming Language used in Sixth Sense Technology is C#.

Fig: Working of Sixth Sense Technology

As mention in definition the sixth sense technology is a technology, which let to interact with physical world and digital world. The most interesting point of sixth sense technology is it often captures our hand gesture to transport the data (pixel) from digital world to physical world. This happened because we use pattern recognition.

SixthSense is a gesture-based wearable computer system developed at MIT Media Lab by Steve Mann in 1994 and 1997 (headworn gestural interface), and 1998 (neckworn version), and further developed by Pranav Mistry (also at MIT Media Lab), in 2009, both of whom developed both hardware and software for both headworn and neckworn versions of it. It comprises a headworn or neck-worn pendant that contains both a data projector and camera. Headworn versions were built at MIT Media Lab in 1997 (by Mann) that combined cameras and illumination systems for interactive photographic art, and also included gesture recognition (e.g. finger-tracking using colored tape on the fingers)[3][4][5][6].

Intuition Synergism

The synergism of A.I and Sixth Sense Technology can create the something like the real intuition of gesture and machine human reaction. Human will start talking with the computer. The interaction between the Computer and Humans will be massive. The gesture will help the computer to realize the command without speaking with each other.

So adding machine learning language and other field like problem solving technology, reasoning, voice technology and many more can make the device more efficient, wonderful and far more Futuristic.

Possible Uses:-

Computer Operating System.

- 1) Transferring Data Through Physical Component (Even Huge Amount Data Amount Of Data Can Be Transfer)
- 2) Hand Gesture and Voice recognition will make the mobile camera Useless

Conclusion:

Artificial Intelligence makes machine intelligent, as machine start reacting like human beings. And Sixth Sense Technology captures the gesture through the camera which makes digital world interact with physical world. It is more advance and futuristic technology. The synergism of both technologies can also overcome their drawbacks. It can change the world.

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